

Attitudes Towards Democracy Post Arab-Spring: Age, Period, Cohort Analysis

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The Arab uprisings sparked widespread hopes for democracy. Scholars have extensively studied the 2011 uprisings and their consequences on collective action (Hoffman and Jamal 2014; Patel, Bunce, and Wolchik 2014), voting behavior (Mehrez 2023; Mehrez et al. 2023; Ozen 2018), regime preferences (Tessler and Robbins 2014), and value change (Moaddel and Gelfand 2017). Central to this literature is the idea that the Arab Spring has left a lasting impact on people's political attitudes – particularly attitudes towards democracy – with notable generational differences. To what extent has the Arab Spring shifted people's political attitudes? And did its influence vary across cohorts, or did all age groups experience similar changes?

Scholars across disciplines have long studied how age (A), period (P), and cohort (C) shape people's attitudes, beliefs, and health conditions over time. In APC analysis, age refers to the individual's biological age, period refers to the specific point in time during which the individual is observed, and cohort referring to an individual's membership in a group defined by a birth year range. A major challenge in these studies is “the identification problem” - the perfect collinearity between these factors, as age = period – birth year (with cohort assignment being

completely dependent on birth year). This relationship makes it impossible to simultaneously estimate the linear effects of all three variables. How do scholars address this issue?

This essay provides a brief demonstration of an APC analysis using a widely adopted methodological approach. I examine attitudes towards democracy among Arab publics following the Arab Spring – an extensively debated topic in Middle Eastern political science literature but, to the best of my knowledge, rarely subjected to empirical testing.

APC analysis

To examine the relationship between support for democracy and the interplay of age, period, and cohort effects in the Arab world, I use Generalized Additive Models (GAM). Unlike other standard linear models, which assume a constant relationship between independent and dependent variable, GAMs allow for the estimated coefficients on the regressors to vary smoothly over time. This approach is particularly appropriate for studying political attitudes, as these attitudes rarely evolve at a constant rate over time; instead, they are shaped by external events and cultural and institutional shifts. Second, GAMs help mitigate the collinearity between A, P, C by

allowing separate smooth functions for age, period, and cohort effects. Third, GAMs effectively handle nested data structures by incorporating country-level variation as random effects. This approach reduces the bias from country-specific characteristics and produces more reliable estimates.

Data

This essay relies on cross-sectional data¹ from five waves of the Arab Barometer (wave II: 2010-2011, wave III: 2012-2014, wave V: 2018-2019, wave VII: 2021-2022 and wave VIII: 2023-2024). To capture attitudes towards democracy, I use the following question: To what extent do you agree with the following statement: “Democratic systems may have problems, yet they are better than other systems.” This question is measured on a 4-point scale where 1 means strongly agree and 4 means strongly disagree. This question was reverse coded so that higher values mean more support for democracy. As predictors, I use age of the surveyed respondents, the survey wave (period), and cohort membership. The cohort variable is categorized based on respondents’ age in 2011— the year when the Arab Spring started. I identified two cohorts:

- Arab Spring Cohort (ages 18–25 in 2011): Individuals who were young adults during the uprisings and possibly shaped by this period of political mobilization.
- Pre-Arab Spring Cohort (ages 35–42 in 2011): Individuals who reached adulthood before the uprisings and presumably had formative political experiences in the pre-2011 era.

I assign respondents to these cohorts based on their reported age in different survey waves. For example, the Arab Spring cohort—defined as those aged 18² to 25 in 2011—progresses through survey waves as follows: 20-27 in 2013, 25-32 in 2018, 29-36 in 2022, and 31-38 in 2024. The same is done with the pre-Arab Spring cohorts who reported age 35-42 in 2011.³ By structuring the data this way, we can investigate whether democratic attitudes in the Arab world are influenced by age, period, or cohort effects during the Arab Spring.

Results

First, I fit a GAM that includes smooth effects for survey wave (period) and age, while controlling for respondents’ education level, religiosity, gender, cohort group, and accounting for country-level random effects.⁴ The partial effect plots for both wave year and age are presented in Figures 1a and 1b.

The results of the smooth effects of wave year (Figure 1a) show a downward trend in support for democracy from 2011 to 2018 which flattens after 2018. The smooth effects of age (Figure 1b) exhibit a positive trend with wide confidence intervals at the extremes (fewer observations). The trend is relatively flat for people aged between 20 and 30. However, from age 30 onward, there is an increasingly positive relationship between age and support for democracy. In other words, support for democracy increases with age. When controlling for cohort membership in the model, the linear effect of becoming politically aware before the Arab Spring is small and not

1 While it is more common to use panel data to trace different cohorts over time (the same individual interviewed over time), cross-sectional data is also used in cohort analysis. See Yang and Land (2008).

2 The Arab Barometer data only surveys people aged 18 and older.

3 I apply a 10-year gap between the two cohorts to avoid any overlapping years.

4 The countries included in this analysis are Algeria, Egypt, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Tunisia, and Yemen.

Figure 1a: Smooth effects of wave year

Figure 1b: Smooth effects of age

statistically significant ($\beta = -0.019, p = 0.638$), suggesting no meaningful difference in democratic attitudes compared to the post-Arab Spring cohort.

To test for the smooth effects of cohort groups, I fit another GAM where I include

the interaction term between survey wave and cohort which allows each cohort group to have its own smoothed trend over time while keeping the smooth effects for age. Smooth effect plots for wave year for Arab Spring vs. pre-Arab Spring cohorts are presented in Figures 2a and 2b respectively.

Figure 2a: Interaction between wave year and Arab Spring cohort

Figure 2b: Interaction between wave year and pre-Arab Spring cohort

The smooth effects of wave year for Arab Spring cohorts does not significantly differ from the one for pre-Arab Spring cohorts. To test which model best fits the data, I compare the previous model (restricted) to the more complex one with the interaction using ANOVA. The F-test results ($F=1.2202$, $p\text{-value} = 0.2907$) suggest that the model with the interaction does not significantly improve model fit compared to the simpler model. This indicates that there is no evidence of cohort specific trends. While this analysis does not detect any differences between cohorts using the available data, it does not necessarily mean that there are no differences. The results are based on a single indicator of democratic attitudes; using a more comprehensive index or alternative conceptualizations of democracy may yield different findings. Additionally, how cohort membership is defined plays a critical role. This essay employs a simple two-group cohort distinction for illustrative purposes, but more theoretically grounded cohort classifications could provide deeper insights.

Conclusion

APC analysis offers researchers the opportunity to explore temporal dynamics, but it also presents several challenges – particularly the identification problem discussed above. This essay only scratches the surface of an important yet problematic question in Middle East studies: How did the Arab Spring affect Arabs' attitudes toward democracy? Moving forward, scholars employing APC frameworks should anchor their work in robust theoretical foundations that explicitly justify their assumptions about age, period, and cohort effects. Furthermore, researchers must apply appropriate statistical techniques while acknowledging their limitations at the same time. ♦

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